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**Acceptance and compliance
to ultra-hypofractionated
postoperative radiotherapy
in patients with
early breast cancer in University clinic
for radiotherapy and oncology, Skopje**

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Introduction: Whole breast radiotherapy (WBRT) is essential treatment strategy in breast cancer treatment. Hypofractionated radiotherapy is standard of care in all stages of early breast cancer. Ultra-hypofractionation is more appropriate and accepted in patients with tumors with early stages.

Materials and methods: The initial implementation of ultra-hypofractionated postoperative radiotherapy in patients with early breast cancer was conducted as prospective-retrospective clinical study approved by the Ethic committee for human research, Faculty of medicine, Skopje. Patients with early breast cancer older than 50 years, with breast-conserving surgery and T1-2/ N0-1 were recruited. They were offered ultra-hypofractionated regimen (26Gy, 5 fraction, one week) with signed consent or the standard hypofractionated regiment (40,5-42,2Gy, 15-16 fractions, 3 weeks). Patients were evaluated with standardized interview after finishing radiotherapy and 4 weeks later.

Results: 44 patients were recruited according to the inclusion criteria of the clinical study. 41 of them signed consent for the ultra-hypofractionated regimen. All of them made this decision because they preferred shorter clinical visits. All of the patients successfully completed the treatment in one week and didn't have any discomfort. On the four week follow up, none of the patients had any uncertainty about their choice.

Conclusion: Ultrahypofractionated WBRT 26 Gy, 5 fractions in one week has a good tolerability and is well accepted in patients with early breast cancer.

Keywords: ultra-hypofractionation, breast cancer

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